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Acceptability and Nutritional Value of Dragon Fruit Peel and Banana Peel Condiment

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Abstract

This study was conducted to develop a condiment made of dragon fruit peel and banana peel. It sought to find out the sensory and general acceptability and analyzed the nutritive value of the developed condiment. Experimental research design product development was used. Using sensory rating scale with nine-point hedonic scale, there were 40 students who served as evaluator in terms of sensory and acceptability. On the other hand, the moisture, ash, crude fiber, crude fat, and crude protein was determined by the First Analytical Services and Technical Cooperative (F.A.S.T.) Laboratories, Los Banos, Laguna, while the phenolic content and antioxidant activity was analyzed at Laboratory, National Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology (BIOTTECH), University of Philippines Los Banos, Laguna. Results shows that the three proportions (75%DFP - 25%BP, 25%DFP - 25%BP, and 25% DFP - 75%BP) of condiments out of dragon fruit peel and banana peel, sample A (75% DFP - 25% BP) has the highest mean score in terms of appearance, texture, and taste. Likewise, sample B (25% DFP - 25% BP) has highest mean score in terms of aroma. Also, the DFP and BP has no nutritive value moisture of 88.3, ash of 2.16, protein of .0854, fat of 0.153, and crude fat of 1.50. As to the phenolic content and antioxidant capacity, results showed that the dragon fruit peel and banana peel condiment (Sample A) had lower radical scavenging activity compared to ascorbic acid in all concentrations tested. Thus, ascorbic acid has a lower EC50 value of 23.38 ug than dragon fruit peel and banana peel condiment phenolics. The condiment is not as good a product as the existing condiments. Most reactions of respondents showed that the texture was not fine compared to the existing condiments. The strong aroma of condiment has a sting effect. It is recommended that the developed condiment made of DFP and the BP is not recommended for people's diet. Another study and test should be conducted to find out its usability and marketability.

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